

Kinetics of Oxidation of Organic Compounds: Part V. Oxidation of Maleic and Fumaric Acids by Cobaltic Sulphate

M. Aijaz Beg and Firoz Ahmed

Kinetics of oxidation of maleic and fumaric acids by cobaltic sulphate has been studied by measuring the disappearance of the oxidant iodometrically. The reaction shows first order dependence on the concentration of the oxidant and gives complex behaviour with the concentration of the substrate. The rate of the reaction is retarded by increasing ionic strength and hydrogen ion concentration. A probable mechanism involving attack of $\text{Co}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ on the double bond has been proposed.

Conant and Aston¹ were, most probably first to use cobaltic sulphate as an oxidising agent. Later on, Swann and Xanthakos² studied the oxidation of several compounds by this reagent. They found that the oxidation of maleic and tartaric acids give formic acid as the end product. It may seem strange that formic acid is completely oxidised by cobaltic sulphate, but it remains unoxidised in the presence of some other substrates, such as amylene and glycine. It is perhaps because of the fact that formic acid might be more difficult to be oxidised than the other compounds. However, these authors have not carried out any kinetic investigations. Bawn and White³ have studied the oxidation of formic acid and alcohols and they have suggested that cobaltic sulphate itself reacts with organic compounds and does not act merely as a source of producing hydroxyl radicals. Hergreaves and Sutcliffe⁴ carried out a kinetic investigation of the oxidation of formaldehyde by the same reagent. They have also made a preliminary study of the sulphate complex of cobaltic ion. According to them, cobaltic ion forms different complexes with sulphate ion, such as, $\text{Co}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$ and CoSO_4^+ .

EXPERIMENTAL

Cobaltic sulphate was prepared from cobaltous sulphate by electrolytic oxidation as described by Swann and Santhakos (loc. cit.). It was standardised by the following method; 2 ml. of the cobaltic sulphate solution was mixed with 8 ml. water and 0.8 gm. (approx.) potassium iodide, the liberated iodine was titrated against standard thiosulphate. Initial dilution of the cobaltic sulphate solution was necessitated by the fact that the sulphuric acid content in the cobaltic sulphate solution was fairly high and it resulted in the liberation of iodine from potassium iodide. It was found by repeated experiments that titration results were reproducible and correct. All other solutions were prepared by weighing AnalaR or B.D.H. grade reagents.

1. J. B. Conant and J. S. Aston, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2783.
2. S. Swann and J. S. Xanthakos, *Ibid.*, 1931, 53, 400.
3. C. E. H. Bawn and A. G. White, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 151, 330.
4. G. Hergreaves and L. H. Sutcliffe, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, 786.

Formic acid and carbon dioxide are the end product of the reaction. Formic acid was detected by chromotropic acid test.⁵ Since this identification involves the development of a purple colour in the end, the colour of cobaltic sulphate was found to mask the test. But a test performed with the distillate of the reaction mixture (when cobaltic sulphate content has been exhausted) verified the presence of formic acid in both the cases. However, all attempts to make quantitative analysis with this test failed poorly. Ionic strength of the medium was maintained by adding requisite amount of medium perchlorate. For the calculation of ionic strength and hydrogen ion concentration it has been assumed that sulphuric acid is completely dissociated to first degree but the second dissociation has been neglected.⁶

Measurements : It appears that both the reactions, i.e., the oxidation of maleic and fumaric acids follows the same mechanism. No standard rate equation fits the experimental data. Therefore, it was thought desirable to find the value of the rate at initial stages. For this, first of all from c (concentration of the oxidant at time t) and time, $\Delta c/\Delta t$ and the corresponding amount of the oxidant reacted (x) were calculated. Then a plot between $\Delta c/\Delta t$ and x gave the initial rate at $x = 0$ (fig. 1). An exactly similar procedure has been adopted by Fudge for the calculation of initial rate.⁷ Assuming the form of the rate expression to be

$$\Delta \text{Co(III)}/\Delta t = k_a[\text{Co(III)}][\text{S}]/k_b + [\text{S}]$$

FIG. 1: Plots of $\Delta c/\Delta t$ vs. x (moles of the oxidant consumed) for the determination of initial rates.

the values of k_a and k_b have been calculated for maleic and fumaric acid reactions, from these values the initial rate has been calculated for each run. The values of these initial rates are close enough to the observed values and this justifies the above rate expression.

A plot between $1/\text{initial rate}$ and $1/\text{substrate}$ gives a straight line which also verifies the proposed rate expression (fig. 3).

Influence of the Hydrogen Ion : The rate of oxidation of maleic acid as well as that of fumaric acid is found to be retarded by increasing concentration of hydrogen ion. It is found that at higher concentration of hydrogen ion a plot between $1/[\text{H}^+]^2$ (Table III)

5. W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 339.
6. C. E. H. Bawn and A. G. White, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 342.
7. A. J. Fudge and K. W. Sykes, *Ibid*, 1952, 119.

TABLE I

Temp. = 20°; $\text{CoSO}_4 = 0.40\text{M}$; $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 2.0\text{M}$; $K_a = .0880$ $K_b = .043$

$\text{Co}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ Mole l^{-1}	Maleic Acid Moles l^{-1}	Initial rate Obs.	10^4 mole $l^{-1} \text{mm}^{-1}$. Calcd.
0.02	0.02	5.6	5.6
0.02	0.05	9.5	9.4
0.02	0.08	11.5	11.2
0.02	0.16	13.4	13.4
0.01	0.02	2.8	2.8
0.01	0.05	4.9	4.7
0.01	0.06	5.4	5.2

TABLE II

Temp. 20°; $\text{CoSO}_4 = 0.4\text{M}$; $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 2.0\text{M}$; $K_b = 0.425$; $K_a = 0.054$

$\text{Co}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ Mole l^{-1}	Fumaric Acid Mole l^{-1}	Initial rate 10^4 Obs.	$\text{mole}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$. Calcd.
0.040	0.040	9.0	9.2
0.040	0.025	8.0	7.9
0.040	0.020	7.0	7.3
0.040	0.010	5.7	5.7
0.032	0.010	4.4	4.7
0.032	0.005	3.4	3.3
0.020	0.020	4.0	3.6
0.020	0.010	2.7	2.9

versus initial rate gives linear relation as shown in fig. 2 Intercept on X-axis appears to indicate the limiting concentration of hydrogen ion where the reaction is completely inhibited.

Fig. 2: Dependence of initial rates on hydrogen ion concentration.

TABLE III

*Influence of hydrogen ion concentration on the initial rates*Temp. 20°; $\text{Co}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 = .01\text{M}$; $\text{CoSO}_4 = .20\text{M}$;

Maleic Acid = .04M or Fumaric Acid = .01M.

[H ⁺] moles l ⁻¹	1/[H ⁺] ²	Initial rate 10 ⁴ Maleic acid	mole l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹ Fumaric Acid
2.65	0.14	6.2	2.5
2.75	0.13	5.4	2.0
2.95	0.11	4.3	1.5
3.45	0.08	2.8	0.9
3.95	0.06	1.6	0.6

Influence of cobaltous sulphate : It was noted that the initial rate of the oxidation reaction of maleic acid was depressed slightly by the increasing concentration of cobaltous ion. But the fumaric acid reaction was found to remain unaffected by the variation of cobaltous sulphate content in the reaction mixture. Waters⁸ has also noticed a slight inhibitory effect of cobaltous ion on the oxidation of diethyl ketone but he could not attach to it any mechanistic significance. Perhaps the different behaviour of the cobaltous ion in the present case may be explained in terms of complex formation of cobaltous ion through the two carboxalate groups of the substrate. Thus with maleic acid, the rate is retarded whereas with fumaric acid the rate of the reaction remains unaffected. However, no experimental evidence can be furnished to support this view, because neither conductometric studies nor spectrophotometric studies indicates any complex formation between cobaltous ion and maleic acid. Ionic strength and sulphate content of the reaction mixture were maintained by adding requisite amount of sodium bisulphate.

TABLE IV

Temp. 20°; $\text{Co}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 = .02\text{M}$; $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 3.1\text{M}$; Maleic acid = .05M.

$\text{CoSO}_4(\text{M})$	0.2	0.30	0.50	0.80	0.90	1.09
Initial rate mole l ⁻¹ min. ⁻¹ 10 ⁴	9.2	7.7	6.9	5.7	5.3	5.0

Influence of ionic strength : The reaction of maleic acids, as well as that of fumaric, shows a negative salt effect. Ionic strength of the reaction mixture has been regulated by sodium perchlorate. Initial rates at various ionic strengths are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

Influence of the ionic strength on the initial rates
 Temp. 20°; $\text{Co}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 = .027$; $\text{CoSO}_4 = .1\text{M}$; $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 2.5\text{M}$;
 Maleic Acid = .05M or Fumaric Acid = .01

Ionic strength	3.5	4.0	4.5	5.0	5.5	6.5
$10^4 \times \text{Initial rate mole l}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. (Maleic acid)	5.4	4.8	4.4	3.8	3.1	2.1
$10^4 \times \text{Initial rate moles l}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. (Maleic acid)	3.4	2.8	2.6	1.5	1.2	—

Temperature dependence: Both the reactions were studied at six different temperatures. It is found that a plot between $\log(k)$ and $1/T$ does not fall in a straight line. Therefore, no thermodynamic functions could be calculated. Hoare and Waters⁹ have also noticed similar behaviour in the oxidation of methyl alcohol. They attributed this abnormality to the complexity of the reaction. As these initial rates have no specific significance, we are not presenting them here.

Fig 3

FIG 3: Dependence of initial rates on substrate concentration.

DISCUSSION

The reduction of cobaltic sulphate has been studied in detail by Bawn and others and it is reported to be quite fast. However, under conditions of our experiment, it is found that only 5% of cobaltic sulphate consumed in 120 min, whereas under similar conditions of temperature and reactant concentrations and in the presence of substrate, cobaltic sulphate was exhausted in 60-70 min. Therefore, self-decomposition of cobaltic sulphate has been neglected in evaluating different rates.

In some cases it is found that oxidation of the substrate yielded formic acid as the end product. Even, quantitative yield has been reported in the oxidation of formaldehyde. It is found that under identical conditions of experiment oxidation of tartaric acid was complete within two minutes, while that of maleic acid lasted for 50-60 min, and formic acid oxidation took 100 min. Therefore, it is assumed that formic acid is oxidised to a very small extent in the presence of maleic or fumaric acid.

9. D. C. Hoare and W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 965.

As oxidation of maleic and fumaric acids follow the same kinetics, it is assumed that they follow the same mechanism. It is likely, therefore, that, firstly, a complex is formed through the double bond of the substrate and not through the carboxylate groups; then this complex slowly breaks down to give products.

The considerable negative salt effect is perhaps due to the presence of an equilibrium preceding the slowest step, which is not favoured by increasing ionic strength. Some negative salt effect has been also found in reactions involving interaction between charge species and uncharged molecule in the slowest step. In view of these facts, a possible mechanism which gives an appropriate rate law is given below :

The rate of disappearance of cobaltic ion is given as :

$$\frac{-d[\text{Co}^{3+}]}{dt} = k_4[\text{complex}^-]$$

Applying the steady state treatment for the complex and $\text{Co}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$,

$$\frac{-d[\text{Co}^{3+}]}{dt} = k_3[\text{S}][\text{Co}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-]$$

and

$$\text{Co}(\text{SO}_4)_2^- = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{Co}^{3+}][\text{HSO}_4^-]}{[\text{H}^+]\{k_3[\text{S}] + k_{-2}[\text{H}^+]\}}$$

But in any run the concentration of HSO_4^- is very large and it may be taken as constant. Putting $k = k_1 k_2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2$ we have :

$$\frac{d[\text{Co}^{3+}]}{dt} = \frac{[\text{S}]}{\{k_3[\text{S}] + k_{-2}[\text{H}^+]\}} \frac{[\text{Co}^{3+}]}{[\text{H}^+]}$$

If it is assumed that k_3 and k_{-2} are of the same order, the above equation simplifies to:

$$\frac{-d[\text{Co}^{3+}]}{dt} = K \frac{[\text{S}]}{K_3[\text{H}^+]^2} [\text{Co}^{3+}]$$

at higher concentration of hydrogen ion. A linear plot between $1/[\text{H}^+]^2$ and initial rate as shown in fig. 1 verifies the above rate law. This scheme and the rate expression also support the order with respect to the oxidant and the complex behaviour of the substrate.

It is difficult to give a definite structure of the complex. It is probable, however, that $\text{Co}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$ interacts with the double bond of the substrate and withdraws one electron from it; this leaves the substrate molecule deficient by one electron. Then the reaction might proceed through carbonium ion as an intermediate to give tartaric acid which is further oxidised to formic acid and carbon dioxide.

A probable schematic representation of the mechanism is given below:

We take this opportunity to thank Professor A. R. Kidwai for providing facilities. One of us (F.A.) wishes to thank CSIR (India) for financial support.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
ALIGARH MUSLIM UNIVERSITY,
ALIGARH.

Received December 19, 1968.